

IMAGE RECOGNITION USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR A SAFETY SYSTEM OF THE DOBOT MAGICIAN

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Abstract – This study aims to enhance the safety of laboratory environments involving Dobot Magician robotic arms by implementing an image recognition-based safety system. The system is designed to prevent accidents and protect both the physical integrity of students and the robotic equipment. By detecting unauthorized objects within the robot's workspace, the system triggers an electrical signal to halt the robot's operation, thereby minimizing potential risks.

Keywords: Image Recognition; Safety; Artificial Intelligence; Dobot Magician.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, automated systems are increasingly utilized because they can enhance various aspects of an industry, improving production, reducing the impact of time in maintenance, decreasing human failure and material waste [1], among other numerous benefits and areas they can offer.

Various types of robots are used in the industry, with a particular emphasis on collaborative robots (cobots), which will be considered in this article. Collaborative robots, are those that can be used alongside human actions in a shared space [2], serving to assist human work by making it more efficient, faster, and productive. One type of these robots are the Robotic Arms, appearing in different areas like health assistance, industrial automation, space exploration, among others [3]

On the other hand, these types of robots may lack the capability to take actions to prevent accidents, as they are programmed solely to execute the motions they have been assigned. Consequently, various safety systems have been developed to mitigate potential accidents, caused by interactions between humans and machines [4]. Some of these systems include torque detection mechanisms that adjust the robot's velocity and power, sensors that delineate the robot's operational areas while maintaining control, and manual control options that enable human operators to perform specific functions.

With the growing use of collaborative robots and recent advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), the main objective of this article is to develop a safety system for the Dobot Magician, an educational robotic arm. This system utilizes an image recognition to detect the human's presence, like a hand in the robot workspace, and safely halt its operation when necessary.

For the implementation of this system, one of the focuses is the embedded AI, which in this article was developed using the Edge Impulse platform, that is an application for machine learning, focused on edge devices. It enables the creation of embedded AI models directly on low-power sensors and devices. The platform simplifies data collection, analysis and model training, making it easier to deploy real-time machine learning solutions on devices with limited computational resources, without requiring internet connectivity.

Thus, using the Edge Impulse, it enables the implementation of an AI system on microcontrollers or other embedded devices, allowing it to operate independently from other systems, while still being able to communicate with them. This makes it possible to integrate the system into existing ones, in a simpler and more efficient manner.

With the embedded safety system, the risk of accidents involving robotic arms is significantly reduced, especially for models like the Dobot Magician, which don't have built-in safety mechanisms.

In summary, the use of Edge Impulse to create an AI in a low-power device for safety, allows this type of system to be inserted in different processes in which it was not included before. Therefore, this project aims to apply the security system in a simple robotic arm, adding a collaborative layer to the system, helping to prevent damage to the arm itself and avoiding accidents for its users.

METHODOLOGY

This project uses a microcontroller from Seeed Studio, XIAO ESP32S3 Sense, to embed an AI. For the built-in camera sensor, it was used a OV2640 that allows the image to be captured. Besides that, an optocoupler had to be included to isolate different electrical parts between the robot and the board, ensuring that the signal from the board do not damage the robot. Figure 1 illustrates the pinout of the XIAO ESP32S3.

Figure 1 - XIAO ESP32S3 Sense Pin List

Although all pins are presented, only one Digital pin, chosen and defined by programming, and the Ground pin (GND) are utilized for this project, along with the camera communication, which is not detailed here. These pins send a 3.3 V signal to the optocoupler whenever an interference (human hand) is detected in the robot's workspace.

Figure 2 shows the representation of the GP5 port, one of the I/O ports of the Dobot Magician, along with its pin configuration, this port allows the robot to receive external signals. Among the pins available in the GP5 port, the 5V and GND pins will be primarily used.

Figure 2 - Representation of GP5 Dobot Port

Figure 3 presents a schematic of the project connections, including the optocoupler (Acoplador Óptico - PORTUGUESE), which is mounted on a board with an LED to visually indicate the transmitted signal, a pull-down resistor to ensure a stable logical signal of 0 when no signal is sent, and a dedicated cable for connection to the Dobot Magician. These components ensure electrical safety by preventing poor contact or incorrect pin connections between the system and the robot.

Figure 3 - Scheme of project connections

In the Edge Impulse platform, a dataset of 86 images, captured by the authors, was created to depict different hand positions within the robot's workspace. The dataset plays a crucial role in AI development, as larger datasets generally lead to better results in training and testing the model. The platform randomly selects these images for use in the training and testing phases of the AI model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Edge Impulse, two labels were defined for the AI in this project: "Dobot," representing the Dobot Magician, and "Interferência" representing an interference in the workspace. Figure 4 illustrates the distinction between these labels within the program.

Using these labels, the AI distinguishes between the movements of the robotic arm and the presence of a human hand in the workspace. When a human hand is detected, a digital signal is sent to the robot to halt its operation.

Figure 5 presents the Confusion Matrix generated by Edge Impulse, which differentiates between the two data labels and highlights the classification accuracy. The label "Interferência" shows some inconsistency in the tests, with an accuracy of 75%.

However, the overall performance of the AI model was satisfactory.

Figure 4 - Labels in AI

Last training performance (validation set)

F1 SCORE
93.3%

Confusion matrix (validation set)

	BACKGROUND	DOBOT	INTERFERÊNCIA
BACKGROUND	100%	0%	0%
DOBOT	0%	100%	0%
INTERFERÊNCIA	25%	0%	75%
F1 SCORE	0.99	1.00	0.86

Figure 5 - AI Confusion Matrix

Edge Impulse enables the creation, training, and testing of an AI model. However, to generate a digital signal, additional code must be implemented. Once the AI distinguishes between the two labels, the program must detect when the "Interferência" label is identified, thereby activating the digital pin on the XIAO ESP32S3 to send the signal. The robot's programming has specific requirements, as it must first check whether the signal received at the GP5 port is logically equal to 0, indicating that no digital signal is being sent and the workspace is clear, before executing any programmed movements. In addition to the previously mentioned inconsistency, the digital signal was successfully transmitted each time the "Interferência" label was identified, effectively halting the robot's movements.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this article was to create a security system for the Dobot Magician robotic arm, utilizing artificial intelligence development based on image recognition. Tests conducted with an AI embedded in the XIAO ESP32S3 demonstrated satisfactory accuracy, allowing the system to effectively halt the robot's movements. However, some inconsistencies were observed in the tests due

to the partial accuracy of the "Interferência" label. To enhance this project, retraining the AI model should be considered. Additionally, increasing the dataset size by providing the Edge Impulse platform with more images for training and testing is essential for achieving better results.

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